

Deep CNN based Image Denoising under Different Noise Conditions

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Abstract--- This Proposed work gives a survey by comparing the different techniques of image denoising with the help of wavelet transforms. To get the better method for Image denoising, there is different merging which have been used. The vital role of communication is transmitting visual information in the appearance of digital images, but at the receiver side we will get the image with corruption. Therefore, in Functional analysis and statistics, the effective image denoising method is still a valid challenge. The algorithms which are very useful for processing the signal like compression of image and denoising the image is Wavelet transforms. To get a high quality image as output, denoising methods includes the maneuver of data of that image. The main aim is wavelet coefficient modification in the new basis, by that the noise in the image data can be eliminated. In this paper, we proposed different methods of image denoising from the corrupted images with the help of different noises like Gaussian and speckle noises. This paper implemented by using adaptive wavelet threshold(Sure Shrink, Block Shrink, Neigh Shrink and Bivariate Shrink) and the experimental results calculate the PSNR and MSE terms to know the comparative accuracy of our proposed work.

Keywords--- Wavelet Thresholding, Sure Shrink, Block Shrink, Neigh Shrink, Bivariate Shrink.

I. Introduction

In acquisition and transmission process, the image is get affected by the noise. Therefore we are using different image denoising techniques to remove the noise from the image. The main aim of image denoising is getting a better quality of original image from the corrupted image. While protecting the characteristics of a signal, Wavelet denoising methods removes the signal noise, without considering the content of frequency. Noise effected natural images denoising is very effective by using wavelet techniques because in few energy transform values only it has the ability to capture the signal energy. Wavelet thresholding technique is used to exploit the wavelet transform capabilities for denoising the signal. It expels noise by killing coefficients that are unimportant in respect to some threshold, and ends up being simple and successful, relies upon the decision of thresholding parameter and the decision of this edge decides, as it were, the adequacy of denoising. Denoising algorithm by using wavelet transform contains three steps.

- Applying wavelet transform to the signal corrupted by noise.
- According to some rule, wavelet coefficients with noise are modified.
- Applying inverse wavelet transform for the modified coefficients.

The image denoising problem can be formulated as given,

Let $B(i, j)$ denotes noisy image, $A(i, j)$ represents noise-free image and $Z(i, j)$ be the noise

$$B(i, j) = A(i, j) + SZ(i, j) \quad (1)$$

The problem is desired signal estimation with the accuracy in response to a given criteria.

The computed problem in the wavelet domain is given as,

$$Y(i, j) = W(i, j)Z(i, j) \quad (2)$$

Where $Y(i, j)$ indicates the wavelet coefficient with noise, $W(i, j)$ represents true coefficient and $Z(i, j)$ indicates the noise occurred.

An experimental result calculates two parameters such as Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Mean Square Error (MSE). By computing these two parameters, the performance of the image denoising algorithm is analyzed.

II. Wavelet Thresholding

Let $A=\{A_{ij}, i, j=1,2,\dots,M\}$ represents the original image which has to be recovered of $M*M$ matrix, where M indicates some value i.e, integer power of 2. The image is affected by white gaussian noise Z_{ij} during the transmission and the standard deviation is $n_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ and at the end of the receiver, the noisy observations $B_{ij}=A_{ij}+ Z_{ij}$ is obtained. The main aim is A signal estimation from the B_{ij} noisy observations such that MSE is lower. Let W represents the 2-D orthogonal DWT (Discrete Wavelet Transform) and W^{-1} represents the inverse of that. Then $Y=WB$ denotes the matrix with wavelet coefficients of B . B consist of four sub bands i.e, LL, LH, HL and HH. The HHk, HLk, LHk are called as detailed coefficients, where k gives the scale altering from $1,2,\dots,J$ and here J is the total decompositions number. At scale k , $N/2^k*N/2^k$ is the sub band size. The LLJ sub band is the minimum resolution residue. To obtain X , the wavelet thresholding denoising method processes each and every Y coefficients through detailed sub bands with a function of soft threshold. The estimation of denoised signal is inversely transformed to $A=W^{-1} X$. For experiments, we are using soft thresholding instead of hard thresholding because when compared to hard thresholding, soft thresholding gives most visual quality images. Later the reason is discontinuous and especially when the noise is notable, recovered images get corrupted with the artifacts.

Sure Shrink

Sure Shrink is one of the thresholding. In this the threshold which is applied is sub-band adaptive threshold. For each and every particular sub-band an individual threshold is calculated depends upon SURE (Stein’s unbiased estimator for risk), the main aim of the Sure Shrink is mean squared error minimization. Given equation defines the Mean Squared Error,

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{X,Y=1}^n (Z(X,Y) - S(X,Y))^2 \quad (3)$$

Where $Z(X, Y)$ denotes the signal estimate, $S(X, Y)$ denotes the original signal with zero noise and n denotes the signal size. In Sure Shrink, the noise is suppressed by thresholding the coefficients of empirical wavelet. The Sure Shrink threshold is denoted by t^* . And it is formulated as below,

$$t^* = \min(t, \sigma\sqrt{2\log n}) \quad (4)$$

Where t is a value, Stein’s Unbiased Risk Estimator is minimized by that t value. σ indicates the variance of noise. And an estimate of noise level σ was described depends upon the median absolute deviation. Given equation shows the median absolute deviation.

$$\hat{\sigma} = \frac{\text{median}(\{|g_{j-1,k}| : k = 0,1 \dots \dots 2^{j-1} - 1\})}{0.6745} \quad (5)$$

And n denotes image size. It is smoothness adaptive. Smoothness adaptive means, if the image contains the sudden changes or boundaries then the reconstructed image also contains the changes.

Bivariate Shrinkage

Bivariate Shrinkage provides better results for denoising the image based on wavelet transform. Because this Bivariate Shrinkage function depends upon both, parent and its coefficient. Let $w1$ be the coefficient and $w2$ is the parent of that coefficient. (The position of $w2$ is same as the coefficient $w1$, but at the next coarser scale.) Then

$$\begin{aligned} y1 &= w1 + n1 \\ y2 &= w2 + n2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Where $y1$ and $y2$ denotes the $w1$ and $w2$ noisy observations, respectively. And $n1$ and $n2$ represents samples of noise. Then we can formulate

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= W + n \\ \text{where } y &= (y1, y2) \\ w &= (w1, w2) \\ n &= (n1, n2) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Given equation defines the Standard MAP estimator for w given corrupted y ,

$$\hat{w}(y) = \arg_w^{\max} P_w \left(\frac{w}{y} \right) \quad (8)$$

The above equation can also be formulated as

$$\hat{w}(y) = \arg \max_w P_w \left(\frac{W}{y} \right) P_w^{(W)} \quad (9)$$

$$p_n I(n) = \frac{1}{n^2} * \exp(-n1^2 + n2^2 + 2\sigma n^2) \quad (10)$$

According to the bays rule allows coefficient estimation can be established by using the noise probability densities as well as wavelet coefficient prior density. Here we conclude noise as gaussian, and then the noise is formulated as given below

$$p_w(W) = \frac{3}{2\pi\sigma^2} * \exp(-\sqrt{3}\sqrt{W12} + W2^2) / \sigma \quad (11)$$

Coefficients joint in Wavelet transform

$$\hat{w}(y) = \arg \max_w [\log(pn(y - W)) + \log(pw(W))] \quad (12)$$

By using equation (7)

$$\hat{w}(y) = \arg \max_w [\log(P_n(y - W)) + \log(P_w(W))] \quad (13)$$

Let us describe

$$f(w) = \log(P_w(W))$$

Afterwards, by using the equations 5.16 and 5.17

$$\hat{w}(y) = \arg \max_w \left[-\frac{(y_1 - w_1)^2}{2\sigma_n^2} - \frac{(y_2 - w_2)^2}{2\sigma_n^2} + f(w) \right] \quad (14)$$

Above equation is identical to compute the given equations

$$y_1 - \frac{\hat{w}_1}{\sigma_n^2} + f_1(\hat{w}) = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$y_2 - \frac{\hat{w}_2}{\sigma_n^2} + f_2(\hat{w}) = 0 \quad (16)$$

Where f1 and f2 defines f(w) derivatives in accordance to w1 and w2 respectively.

We know that, f(w) can also be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} f(w) &= \log(P_w(W)) \\ f(w) &= \log(P_w(w)) \\ &= \log\left(\frac{3}{2\pi\sigma^2} * \frac{\exp(-\sqrt{3}\sqrt{W1^2} + W2^2)}{\sigma}\right) \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \log\left(\frac{3}{2\pi\sigma^2} - \frac{-\sqrt{3}\sqrt{W1^2} + W2^2}{\sigma}\right) \\ f_1(w) &= -\sqrt{3} \frac{w_1}{\sigma\sqrt{w_1^2}} + w_2^2 \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

$$f_2(w) = -\sqrt{3} \frac{w_2}{\sigma\sqrt{w_1^2}} + w_2^2$$

By using the above equations (15), (16), (17), and (18) , MAP estimator is given as

$$Z_{\hat{w}_1} = \frac{\left(\sqrt{y_1^2 + y_2^2} - \sqrt{3} \frac{\sigma_n^2}{\sigma}\right) + y_1}{\sqrt{y_1^2 + y_2^2}} \quad (19)$$

Neigh Shrink

In the Neigh Shrink thresholding, relating to the 3th magnitude of the squared sum of all the wavelet coefficients, it means, the local energy, Neigh Shrink thresholds the coefficients of wavelet. And the neighborhood window has may be any size. It may be 3*3, 5*5, 7*7, 9*9 etc. A wavelet coefficient is centered with 3*3 neighboring window and to be shrinked is shown in fig 1.

Fig. 1: A Sketch of the neighboring Window with Size 3*3 Centered at Shrunked Wavelet Coefficient

$$\Gamma_{i,j} = \left[1 - \frac{T_U^2}{S_{ij}^2} \right]^+ \quad (20)$$

Here TU represents universal threshold and S_{ij}^2 represents the squared sum of all the coefficients of Wavelet transform in the below window.

$$S_{ij}^2 = \sum_{n=j-1}^{j+1} \sum_{m=i-1}^{i+1} Y_{m,n}^2 \quad (21)$$

Here “+” sign is the very powerful determinant. It keeps the positive value at the end of the formula, it means when it is negative, modifying it into zero. Then, from its noisy counterpart Y_{ij} , the coefficient of estimated center wavelet is determined and it is given as,

$$\hat{F}_{ij} = \Gamma_{ij} \cdot Y_{ij} \quad (23)$$

Block Shrink

Block Shrink is a kind of approach, in which a data-driven block thresholding is done. By using the block thresholding, Block Shrink uses the neighbor wavelet coefficients pertinence. With the minimization of Stein’s Unbiased Risk Estimate (SURE), the optimal size of block can be resolved as well as the every wavelet sub band’s threshold can be determined. The block thresholding at the same time keeps or kills each and every of the coefficients in bunches as opposed to independently. The estimation precision increases in block thresholding by using the neighbor wavelet coefficient information. In the performance of block thresholding estimator, size of block and level of threshold plays a vital role. The above local block thresholding methods have block size and threshold in a fixed value. And the regardless of wavelet coefficient distribution, for all the resolution levels same thresholding rule is applied.

Fig. 2: 2*2 Block Partition for a Wavelet Sub Band

When we apply wavelet decomposition on an image, multiple sub bands are produced, which is given in the figure2. It is need to segment the each sub band into multiple numbers of blocks.

And with the minimization of Stein’s Unbiased Risk Estimate, for each and every sub band, the optimal size of block and threshold can be selected by Block Shrink.

For each and every standard images with their noisy and denoised images, two parameters are calculated. Those are PSNR (Peak Signal to Noise Ratio) and MSE(Mean Square Error). PSNR is defined as the ratio between signals maximum possible power and the corrupting noise power. By this, the representation fidelity is affected. The scale of PSNR is logarithmic decibel. PSNR can be formulated as below,

$$PSNR = 10\log(255/MSE)^2 \quad (24)$$

After denoising the image, PSNR is computed for denoised image also.

The mean squared error (MSE) or mean squared deviation (MSD) of an estimator measures the average of the squares of the errors or deviations—that is, the difference between the estimator and what is estimated. The MSE calculation can be formulated as given below equation.

$$MSE = 1/N \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (X_j - \bar{X}_j)^2 \quad (25)$$

Denoising Using CNN Model

Here, we are proposing denoising CNN model, i.e, DnCNN, and for multiple general image denoising tasks, DnCNN is extended. Normally, for a specified task, training of DnCNN follows mainly two steps: 1) Design of Network Architecture. and 2) Model Learning from Training Data.

Fig. 3: The Architecture of the DnCNN Network

In Design of Network Architecture, to make it suitable for denoising the image, VGG network is modified. Based on the effective patch sizes, set the network depth. That patch sizes are used in state-of-the-art denoising methods. In Model Learning from Training Data, residual learning formulation is adopted, and for speed training and to improve the performance of image denoising, it is incorporated with batch normalization. Finally, the connection between DnCNN and TNRD is discussed and DnCNN is extended for multiple general image denoising tasks.

III. Results

In this paper, different image denoising techniques are analyzed comparatively with the help of Wavelet transforms. Different types of image formats are used in this proposed work like JPG, TIF, PNG and BMP. Experimental results are got by using four methods of thresholding. i.e, Sure Shrink, Neigh Shrink, Bivariate Shrink and Block Shrink. And these thresholding methods using the different images with the noise and reported on the 512*512 standard test image Lena (Figure 3). In experimental results, we are using various types of noises like Gaussian noise, Salt and Pepper noise and Speckle noise with the standard deviation of 10. Finally PSNR and MSE values are calculated.

Fig. 4: Original Image

Fig. 5: Noisy Image

Fig. 6: SURE Shrink Image

Fig. 7: Bivariate Shrinkage Image

Fig. 8: Block Shrink Image

Fig. 9: Neigh Shrink Image

Fig. 10: CNN Training

Fig. 11: Reconstructed Image by Deep CNN

IV. Conclusion

This paper presents a comparative analysis of various image denoising techniques using wavelet transforms. The image formats that have been used in this work are JPG, BMP, TIF and PNG. We have experimented with four different thresholding methods (Sure shrink, Bivariate shrink, Neigh shrink, Block Shrink) using the various noisy images and report the results for the 512×512 standard test images Lena (Fig. 3). They are contaminated with Gaussian noise, salt and paper noise and speckle noise with standard deviations 10. Our results are measured by the PSNR and MSE. By calculating PSNR value as high and MSE as low. By using CNN we can get Reconstructed Original Image.

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